

SOME ETHNO-MEDICINAL PLANTS AND ECO-FRIENDLY NATURAL COLORS YIELDING FLOWERING PLANTS OF B.S.N. GOVT. P.G. COLLEGE CAMPUS, SHAJAPUR (M.P.) – A SURVEY REPORT

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Abstract:

The present work is attempt has been made to compile the some ethno-medicinal plants and eco-friendly natural colors yielding flowering plants their preparations used for cure of diseases and information of flowering plants with the list of plants from B.S.N. Govt. P.G. College campus Shajapur, India. The present study focused on some important plants having medicinal uses and color yielding potential. Now-a-days natural products and herbal medicines have been recommended for the treatment of various diseases. The present study of ethno-medicinal and natural colors yielding flowering plants is helpful for local peoples of Shajapur.

Keywords:

Ethno-medicinal plants, Flowering plants, Natural Colors, Madhya Pradesh.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Ethno-medicinal plants studies the complex relationships between plants and human. It is multidisciplinary science defined as the interaction between plants and human being. The relationship between plants and human being is not limited to the use of plants for food, clothing and shelter but also includes their use for health care, religious ceremonies and ornamentation. Medicinal plants have always been the main sources of medicine in India. Since ancient past and presently they are becoming popular¹⁻⁵. Natural color is one of the elements of nature that made the human living more aesthetic and fascinating. They are supposed to be associated with emotions, human qualities, festivals and passion in our life. In India, there are more than 470 plants that can yield bright colors⁶. Natural dyes are environment friendly such, turmeric, the brightest of naturally occurring yellow color is a powerful antiseptic which revitalizes the skin and many other common natural color yielding plants⁷⁻⁹. Different parts of the plants such as bark, leaves, flowers, etc were used for various purposes. The Study of available literature shows that several studies were carried out on ethno-medicinal and natural color yielding plants in the recent past.

2. STUDY AREA

Shajapur District is a district of Madhya Pradesh state of central India. The town of Shajapur is the district headquarters. Shajapur district is part of the Malwa Plateau. The district is situated in

the northwestern part of the state and lies between latitudes 32°06' and 24° 19' north and longitudes 75° 41' and 77° 02' east. The district is identified from the headquarters town Shajapur named after honor of Shahjahan, the Mughal emperor who halted here in 1640. It is said that the original name was Shahjahanpur, which subsequently reduces to Shajapur. Since the formation of the Gwalior state, it has remained a district. The constructed area of college is 15000 Sq. Meter. College constructed it in 1958. The study site “Naveen-Vatika” and surrounding area is rich in flower and medicinal plants. Floristic composition is the major morphological characters of the plant community. Thus, a detailed survey of the floristic vegetation was carried out in and around the study site¹⁰.

Fig 1: Naveen-Vatika in College Campus, Shajapur

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The survey was focused on the group discussion and talks with local people of Shajapur, totally providing the information of ethno-medicinal and natural colors yielding flowering plants during the study. Data were collected through general conversation with traditional healers and questionnaires were used to obtain the plants used by them. Details of medicinal plants used,

mode of treatment were documented¹¹⁻¹³. Sometimes we also observed various patients coming and having relief.

Test of natural colors in plant parts first is crush the plant part in pestle mortar and smear the crushed plant paste on filter paper, if the color retains on paper, it may be a good source of natural dye. Second is if the color is retained on the fingers even after washing with water, it may be a good source of natural dye with probably good wash fastness. Third is squeeze the plant part preferably flowers and leaves between the fingers if color is discharged, it may be a good source of natural color and last is shake boiled water and put crushed plant part, if it releases color into the water, it may be a source of natural color.

The ethno-medicinal plants and natural colors yielding flowering plants observation recorded and as shown in Table 1 and 2.

Table 1: Ethno-medicinal Plants

Sr. No.	Botanical Name	Local Name	Family	Parts Used	Ethno-medicinal Uses
01	Aegle marmelos L.	Bel	Rutaceae	Fruits	Pulp is directly taken with sugar and Spices for stomach infections.
02	Carica papaya L.	Papita	Caricaceae	Fruit, Seed Powder	Ripened fruits are suggested for jaundice patients, Seed powder is Digesting.
03	Ocimum sanctum	Tulsi	Labiataeae	Leaves	Cough, Cold, bronchitis, expectorants
04	Mentha longifolia L.	Pudina	Lamiaceae	Leaves	Leaves are taken with spices as chatni for abdominal disorders.
05	Zizyphus zuzuba	Ber	Rhamnaceae	Fruit, Seeds	Ripened dried fruits are crushed and powdered, taken with salt and sugar for the cure of indigestion and constipation.
06	Mangifera indica Linn.	Mango	Anacardiaceae	Bark	Mangoes are rich in antioxidants such as beta-carotene, and Vitamin C, Antioxidants have been shown to play an important role in the prevention of cancer and heart disease.

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07	Emblica officinalis	Aawala	Euphorbiaceae	Fruit	Vitamin - C, Cough, Diabetes, cold, Laxative, hyper acidity.
08	Lawsennia iermis	Mehandi	Lytharaceae	Leaf, Seed Flower,	Burning, Steam, Anti Inflammatory.
09	Azardirchata - indica	Neem	Mahaceae	Rhizome	Sedative, analgesic, epilepsy, hypertensive.
10	Psidium gaujava	Amrud	Myrtaceae	Leaves and bark	Disinfectant and antiseptic for dressing wounds and sores. digestive disorders and reduce high blood pressure
11	Cassia fistula	Amaltas	Fabaceae	Fruit, Seed, Pulp, Root	Emetics, purgatives, febrifuges and relievers of thoracic congestion, asthma, leprosy, ringworm, fever.
12	Ficus benghalensis Lin	Bargad	Moraceae	Bark, Leaves	Grinding the pills and making decoction in toxicology. The bark of this therapeutically valuable tree is attributed with tonic, astringent cooling and diuretic properties in ayurveda.
13	Butea monosperma	Palash	Fabaceae	Flower, Bark, Leaves	Diarrhea, Dysentery, Intestinal Worms, Diabetes, Skin Disorders and Retention of urine.
14	Dalbergia sissoo	Shisham	Fabaceae	Leaves, Root	Decoction of leaves is useful in gonorrhea. Root is astringent. Wood is alternatives, useful in leprosy, boils, eruption and to allay vomiting.
15	Calotropis procera	Aakda	Asclepiadaceae	Latex, Leaves, Root	Leprosy, syphilis, malarial, antimicrobial, hepatic protective agents, against colds and coughs, syphilis and elephantiasis, asthma and piles.

Table 2: Eco-friendly natural colors yielding flowering plants

Sr. No.	Botanical Name	Local Name	Family	Parts Used	Natural Color
01	Acacia nilotica Linn.	Babool	Mimosaceae.	Bark	Brown
02	Aegle marmelosn linn.	Bel	Rutaceae	Fruit and Bark	Brown
03	Azadirachta indica.A. Juss	Neem	Meliaceae	Bark	Brown
04	Carica papaya	papita	caricaceae	Leaf and fruits	Green-Orange
05	Thevetia peruviana pers.	Kaner	Apocynaceae	Flower	Pink
06	Delonix regia Rafin.	Gulmoher	Caesalpiniacea	Flower	Red
07	Lawsonia inermis Linn.	Mehndi	Lythraceae	Leaf	Orange
08	Mangifera indica Linn.	Mango	Anacardiaceae	Bark	Brown
09	Nerium oleander Linn.	Kaner	Apocynaceae	Flower	Pink
10	Psidium guajava Linn.	Amrud	Myrtaceae.	Bark	Brown

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The observation and results, it can be reveals that during preliminary survey it was recorded that the B.S.N. Govt. P.G. College campus Shajapur, rich in herbal medicine with diversified ethno-medicinal values and eco friendly natural colors yielding flowering plants. The present study of ethno-medicinal and natural colors yielding flowering plants is also helpful for local peoples of Shajapur.

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